

Photogrammetry and 3D Modelling Applied to the Creation of Virtual Reality in Realistic Environments: Analysis of Free Software for Image Processing

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Abstract

This paper explores the combination of 3D modeling through photogrammetry with low-cost virtual reality (VR). 3D modeling has become an essential tool in various fields, such as civil engineering and architecture, facilitating project visualization. Photogrammetry, defined as the science of obtaining reliable measurements from photographs, allows for the capture of complex environmental details with high precision. However, the traditional use of photogrammetry requires expensive equipment, limiting its accessibility to companies with greater financial resources. With technological advancements, the use of drones and high-resolution satellite imagery has expanded the scope of this technique. This study adopts a low-cost approach, utilizing affordable cameras and free, open-source software to generate 3D models from terrestrial images. The image capture was carried out at the building of the Graduate Program in Modeling (PPGM) at the State University of Feira de Santana (UEFS), using 100 photos processed in three software applications: Meshroom, Colmap, and Regard3D. The research aims to evaluate the quality of the generated 3D models, considering processing time, point cloud, and texturing. The combination of VR with 3D modeling enhances project presentations and feasibility analyses, offering an accessible solution for professionals in civil engineering and architecture, without requiring significant investment in equipment.

1.0 Introduction

The graphical representation of models has been a subject of study for a long time. The use of drawings as a form of expression dates back to prehistoric times, with cave art. In recent decades, the use of graphical alternatives for project reproduction has been adopted by various professionals across different fields. Over the years, as human beings sought to evolve in various ways, technology advanced alongside them. Civil Engineering is an example of this evolution. Drawings that were once created freehand, as a limited form of representation, have evolved into a more technical practice, incorporating standards, detailing, and views. From pencils, scale rulers, and paper, the tools of the trade shifted to mouse and keyboard in this new era, with the implementation of CAD (Computer-Aided Design) technology and, later, BIM (Building Information Modeling) technology, which enables the development of projects directly on computers, replacing the manual drawing that was once widely used.

T3D modeling involves the three-dimensional representation of characters or environments, offering enhanced visualization of details in the object being represented, adding depth, and thus enabling various applications that a simple 2D drawing cannot provide. The use of this technology is already a reality. In Brazil, architecture and engineering firms have adopted this tool for project development and presentation. With the aid of software designed for 3D modeling, such as Blender and SketchUp, or tools that utilize BIM technology, it is possible to coordinate projects and develop 3D models, which play a crucial role in the process.

Photogrammetry was defined as "the science and art of obtaining reliable measurements from photographs" (American Society of Photogrammetry). Although it is a powerful technique for capturing environmental details, it involves a complexity of equipment, hardware, and software, which are costly, thus limiting its use to individuals or companies with high purchasing power. However, with the advancement of its techniques and tools, whether through the incorporation of high-resolution

satellite imagery or the integration of drone technology, significant progress has been made. This definition has become more comprehensive as new studies have been conducted. Consequently, 3D modeling through photogrammetry has emerged, allowing the acquisition of data in small formats, enabling large-scale studies with a wealth of detail that can positively contribute to feasibility studies, risk analysis, project presentations, and other applications in fields such as Civil Engineering, Architecture, and Surveying. The combination of these technologies not only enhances project visualization but also optimizes the collection of geospatial data, promoting a more comprehensive and accurate approach.

Given the technological advancements and an increasingly demanding market, there is no choice but to incorporate new technologies into projects, whether for feasibility studies, risk management, or project presentations. The use of Virtual Reality (VR) can offer improvements and efficiency in various sectors, including civil engineering, architecture, surveying, and related fields. Recently, the real estate company MRV Engenharia launched the My Home Experience project, which involves the use of VR in project presentations for clients (MRV, 2018). The combination of 3D models obtained through photogrammetry, using open-source software, with tools that provide virtual reality environment visualization free of charge, will offer professionals the opportunity to enter this technology at a low cost.

This paper will address the combination of 3D modeling from photogrammetry with virtual reality, aiming for a low-cost approach from image capture, processing, and obtaining the final 3D model, to its application in a virtual reality environment, using open-source software, low-cost cameras, and free tools.

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2.0 Methodology

Using the close-range technique, 3D models will be generated from terrestrial photographs captured with a Canon EOS 200D, of the building of the Graduate Program in Modeling (PPGM) at the State University of Feira de Santana (UEFS). A total of 100 photos were obtained and processed using three open-source, free-distribution software tools for image processing: Meshroom, CollMap, and Regard3D.

Figure 1 - Meshroom Software Initial Screen

Meshroom: It is an open-source software used for creating 3D models from photographs. It is a project supported by the AliceVision association, a non-profit organization. It falls into the category of three-dimensional reconstruction programs based on photogrammetry, a technique that uses overlapping photographs to create realistic three-dimensional models. According to the developers, the organization's ambition is to democratize 3D scanning technologies from photographs. Meshroom operates by analyzing a set of images taken from an object or scene from various perspectives. The dense modeling of the scene is achieved through the chaining of two computer vision-based pipelines: "Structure-from-Motion" (SfM) and "Multi-View Stereo" (MVS) (AliceVision).

Colmap: It is an open-source software designed for 3D reconstruction from images, widely used in computer vision and photogrammetry. It is known for its ability to create three-dimensional models from a collection of two-dimensional images. It employs the "Structure-from-Motion" (SfM) technique to estimate three-dimensional geometry from the information contained in 2D images. In addition to SfM, COLMAP also incorporates the "Multi-View Stereo" (MVS) technique, which is used to generate a dense 3D mesh from stereo images. The images used for model creation do not necessarily need to come from professional equipment; the software supports images from smartphones to high-definition cameras. It features a straightforward and user-friendly interface, facilitating learning.

Figure 2 - COLMAP Software Initial Screen

Regard3D: It is an open-source software designed for creating 3D models from two-dimensional images. It is particularly useful for the three-dimensional reconstruction of objects, scenes, or environments from a series of photographs taken from different angles of the object to be transformed into 3D. Its function is to create 3D models from 2D images, utilizing feature matching techniques across multiple images, allowing for triangulation to determine the three-dimensional position of points of interest. It is an easily accessible and user-friendly software, available for Windows and Mac OS X operating systems, but only in 64-bit versions. Its system requirements are significantly lower compared to those required by other similar software.

Figure 3 - Regard3D Software Initial Screen

There is a significant similarity among the selected software, as a results comparison will be conducted with the aim of obtaining the best possible low-cost model. During image processing, various parameters and settings provided by the software will be tested to achieve the best possible outcome, taking into account the limitations of both the software and the hardware. The post-processing stage is crucial in achieving the optimal result for the three-dimensional model, whether performed within the processing software, if it offers such an option, or in another software that allows for necessary optimizations and improvements. Blender is a suitable option for this purpose; being an open-source software, it offers various tools for 3D modeling and encompasses all stages of the 3D process — from modeling, rigging, and animation to simulation, rendering, compositing, motion tracking, as well as features for video editing and game development.

The criteria for evaluating the generated models are defined by the quality of the final model, considering processing time, point cloud, and texture reproduction. The ease of post-processing should also be assessed, as well as the compatibility with the tool used for creating the realistic environment. This environment will be created using the Unreal Engine, a graphics engine developed

by Epic Games. Although widely used in electronic game development, Unreal Engine holds significant potential for applications in Civil Engineering, Architecture, Surveying, and other fields

3.0 Results

For image processing, a low-cost hardware configuration was selected. Initially, 100 images were captured of the building housing the Graduate Program in Modeling (PPGM) at the State University of Feira de Santana (UEFS). Image quality and lighting are fundamental factors that influence the quality of the final 3D model. Zoom is unnecessary, and the focal length must remain consistent across all images. The software used for processing requires that the focal length and sensor width be known parameters in the image metadata. If the software does not recognize the camera used, it is possible to manually input these parameters; however, if these parameters are not accurately aligned with reality, the resulting model may not be satisfactory.

- Processor: Intel Xeon E3-1230 V2 3,3 GHz
- Motherboard: DXH61Z M2 Duex
- Graphics Card: RX580 8GB MingZhou
- RAM: 16GB

Figure 4 - Captured Images

The image processing was carried out using the three previously mentioned software; however, only Regard3D and Meshroom demonstrated acceptable performance on the computer used.

Meshroom offers a drag-and-drop processing interface, eliminating the need for prior study for new users to obtain their first 3D model. The program comes pre-configured with acceptable parameters, resulting in a good point cloud and a satisfactory 3D model. However, if the result does not meet the user's expectations, the parameters can be adjusted to achieve the desired outcome.

Figure 5 - process tree (Meshroom)

Meshroom operates as a process tree, where each step is responsible for a phase of the model reconstruction. The software uses the SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform) algorithm, which identifies and compares discriminative features in different images, regardless of rotation, translation, or scale (AliceVision). After this image matching, the goal is to identify common points between distinct images. Using the Structure from Motion (SfM) technique, which reconstructs a three-dimensional scene from multiple 2D images taken from different angles, the software simultaneously estimates the 3D structure (points in space) and the camera poses (position and orientation). Finally, the point cloud generated in the previous step undergoes a densification and texturization process, resulting in a textured three-dimensional surface based on the provided images. The processing time to obtain the final result was XX hours, and significant CPU and RAM usage was observed, with RAM usage peaking at 85% during certain moments.

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Figure 6 – Point cloud (MeshroomCL)

A difficulty encountered with Meshroom was the need for a machine equipped with CUDA technology, an API developed by Nvidia and utilized by some graphics cards. Computers with AMD graphics cards lack this technology, making it difficult to use the software. However, there is a solution: MeshroomCL, an extension developed to address this issue. While the traditional Meshroom requires CUDA, the extension works with the OpenCL API, which broadens the range of graphical platforms capable of running the software.

Figure 7 – Final model (MeshroomCL)

In a comparison of the generated models, a significant visual difference in texture mapping was observed. The model generated by MeshroomCL exhibited substantial texture flaws, complicating the post-processing, as it will be necessary to redo the texture mapping upon importing it into Blender. Another point

to consider is the density of the models: the Regard3D produced a model with a lower polygon count, facilitating post-processing. It is important to note that the comparison of the models was conducted using standard parameters provided by the software. It is known that parameters can be modified to enhance specific stages; however, based on the tests conducted, a considerable need for a standard of quality and quantity of captured images was identified. If the captured image does not meet this standard, parameters may be adjusted and algorithms applied in order to improve image correspondence.

Unlike Meshroom, Regard3D is not as straightforward when it comes to image processing. Although its interface is quite simple, the user needs prior knowledge of the steps that must be followed. However, an in-depth study of the documentation is not required if the software's default parameters are sufficient. Given that the aim of this study is to achieve the best result at a low cost, it was observed that the default parameters of Regard3D are sufficient to generate a satisfactory result, provided that high-quality images are supplied. The processing time for the chosen parameters was 1 hour to obtain the final model, with some processes, such as mesh computation and densification, taking longer than others. During the process, high CPU and RAM usage was observed, with the majority of the time spent above 60% utilization.

Figure 8 – Point Cloud Model (Regard3D)

Figure 9 – Dense Point Cloud Model (Regard3D)

Figure 10 – 3D Model (Regard3D)

Due to the high usage, particularly of RAM, it is recommended that the machine used for processing have at least 16 GB of RAM. The final file of the three-dimensional model is relatively large. For the model in this study, a file of 5 GB was generated, making it advisable to allocate a substantial amount of internal storage prior to processing.

Regard3D demonstrated the best performance under the established hardware conditions. Additionally, the quality of the generated model, in comparison to the polygon count, was a decisive factor in its selection. The lower polygon count facilitated post-processing in Blender, which included model optimization, removal of unnecessary mesh components, and filling of gaps. This process is relatively straightforward and does not require advanced technical expertise. The model generated by Regard3D also produced a superior texture map, which significantly contributed to its selection.

Figure 11 – model after post-processing and optimization in Blender

Finally, the model, after being processed and optimized, was loaded into the Unreal Engine 5 graphics engine to assess the possibility of combining 3D models generated by photogrammetry with the creation of realistic environments and virtual reality. The result was satisfactory; within the limitations of low-cost software and hardware, the model was adequately exported with its texture generated in Regard3D. It was observed

that the high polygon count would make the model "heavy," potentially requiring a more powerful computer to load it.

Figure 12 – Model running in real-time on Unreal Engine 5

Figure 13 – Model running in real-time on Unreal Engine 5

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Appendix

Figure 14 – Parameters computing matches (Regard3D)

Figure 15 – Correspondences (Regard3D)

Figure 16 – Parameters Densification (Regard3D)

Figure 17 – Parameters surface generation (Regard3D)